

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D3.4

Design controller to realise operational strategy

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable discusses the design of the controller to realise the operational strategy. The controller consists of 5 modes two of which are for below rated wind speeds for which the thrust from the secondary rotors is the sole control action. One mode is concerned with the transition between below rated operation and above rated operation. The final two modes are concerned with above rated operation. The latter three modes have two control actions, specifically, primary blade pitch and secondary rotor thrust.

1 Introduction

The X-rotor operational strategy is discussed in D3.1 [1] and the control related models in D3.2 [2] and D3.3 [3]. As reported in [1], three options for the operation of secondary rotors have been considered, namely, for a given ambient wind speed,

- i. their rotational speed is held constant; that is, it does not vary with primary rotor azimuthal angle
- ii. their tip speed ratio is constant; that is, it does not vary with primary rotor azimuthal angle
- iii. the rotational speed of both secondary rotors is the same with the tip speed ratio of the rotor, when rotating into the ambient wind speed, held constant.

As identified in [1], option (iii) is the preferred strategy. The design of the controller to realise that strategy is described in this report.

2 Operational strategy

The secondary rotors are operated such that both rotate with the same rotor speed. For a given ambient wind speed, the tip speed ratio of the rotor rotating into the ambient wind speed is held constant, the upper curve in Figure 1. Of course, it follows that the tip speed ratio of the secondary rotor rotating away from the ambient wind does not remain constant, the lower curve in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Operating point locus in constant ambient wind speed on the secondary rotor torque, T_S , speed, Ω_S , plane.

The mechanical power extracted by the blade rotating into the ambient wind is

$$P_i = k_i(R_P\Omega_P + V_{S\theta})^3 = k_i(R_P\Omega_P)^3(1 + V_{S\theta}/(R_P\Omega_P))^3$$

where $V_{S\theta}$ is the component of the ambient wind speed perpendicular to the secondary rotor at primary rotor azimuthal angle θ_P , Ω_P is the primary rotor speed, R_P is the radial distance of the secondary rotor from its axis of rotation and k_i is a constant. Hence,

$$P_i = k_i(R_P\Omega_P)^3(1 + \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})^3$$

since

$$V_{S\theta}/(R_P\Omega_P) = \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc} \quad ; \quad \Delta\Omega_S = \Omega_S - \Omega_{Sc}$$

Similarly the mechanical power extracted by the blade rotating out of the ambient wind is

$$P_o = k_o(R_P\Omega_P)^3(1 - \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})^3$$

Note that k_o is no longer a constant but depends on the tip speed ratio of the blade rotating out of the ambient wind

$$\lambda_o = R_S\Omega_S/(R_P\Omega_P - V_{S\theta}) = (R_S\Omega_{Sc})/(R_P\Omega_P)(1 + \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})/(1 - \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})$$

where R_S is the radius of the secondary rotor. The difference between the power generated by the rotor rotating into the ambient wind speed and the power generated by the rotor rotating out of the ambient wind speed is

$$\Delta P = P_i - P_o = k_i(R_P\Omega_P)^3(1 + \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})^3 - k_o(\lambda_o)(R_P\Omega_P)^3(1 - \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})^3$$

which can be solved to determine

$$\Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc} = f(\Delta P) \quad \text{and} \quad \Omega_S = \Omega_{Sc} + f(\Delta P)\Omega_{Sc}$$

Comment

Provided the value of torque coefficient of the secondary rotors, C_{PS} , is kept sufficiently close to its maximum value, C_{PmaxS} , then $k_o \approx k_i$ and

$$\Delta P \approx k(1 + \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})^3 - k(1 - \Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})^3 = 6k\Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc} + 2k(\Delta\Omega_S/\Omega_{Sc})^3$$

where $k = k_i(R_p\Omega_p)^3$. For almost all operating conditions, the additional approximation

$$f(\Delta P) \approx \Delta P/(6k)$$

may suffice when

$$\Omega_S \approx \Omega_{Sc} + \Delta P\Omega_{Sc}/(6k)$$

The complete operational strategy has 5 modes. With respect to the secondary rotors, these are defined in terms of the cusp points, labelled Ω_{Sc} in Figure 1. The modes are described below in order of rising ambient wind speed, namely, below rated constant Ω_{Sc} , C_{Pmax} tracking, pre-emptive pitching, above rated constant primary rotor torque and above rated constant primary rotor power.

2.1 Mode 1: below rated constant Ω_{Sc}

The rotational speed of the cusp point in Figure 1 is held constant such that $\Omega_{Sc} = \Omega_{S0}$. The the required secondary rotor speed is

$$\Omega_S = \Omega_{S0} + f(\Delta P)\Omega_{S0}$$

with ΔP determined as above.

2.2 Mode 2: C_{Pmax} tracking

The cusp point, defined as above, lies on the secondary rotor C_{Pmax} curve and a blade, rotating into the ambient wind, is required to track the same curve, see Figure 1. Hence, maintaining its tip speed at λ_{Pmax} suffices. Of course, the blade rotating out of the ambient wind speed deviates from the C_{Pmax} curve and does not track its C_{Pmax} curve as in Figure 1.

2.3 Above rated operation

The total secondary rotor induced torque arises from essentially tracking C_{Pmax} , albeit slightly modified from the secondary rotors rotating out of the ambient wind over half the rotation, until rated wind speed is reached at b , after which the total torque is essentially held constant, see Figure 2.

Because the wind speed experienced by a secondary rotor oscillates about its nominal value, $R_p\Omega_p$, as the primary rotor rotates, the reaction torque is enhanced by approximately $(1 + \lambda_p^{-2}/2)$. This enhancement increases as ambient wind speed increases and so λ_p decreases. Hence, to maintain a constant secondary induced torque, the cusp point in Figure 1 must be adjusted with increasing wind speed, for which the pitch angle of the primary rotor blades is good surrogate.

Figure 2: Idealised torque wind speed curve

To reduce the maximum rate of pitching between b and c , the operating strategy is modified as indicated by the green curve in Figure 2. The cusp point is required to track this adjustment, which is chosen such that the pitch rate is kept to a minimum.

2.4 Mode 3: pre-emptive pitching

The approach is similar to mode 1 in that the cusp point in Figure 1 is required to track the predetermined curve, the green line in Figure 2. In this case, both blade pitch angle, β , and the tip speed ratio of the secondary rotor blade rotating into the ambient wind.

$$\beta = f(\Omega_P) \quad ; \quad \lambda_{Si} = g(\Omega_{Sc})$$

2.5 Mode 4: above rated constant torque

The primary rotor pitch angle is adjusted to maintain a constant primary rotor speed. The cusp point for the secondary rotors are adjusted to maintain a constant reaction torque so that the primary rotor torque in turn remains constant, see above. However, the secondary rotor power continues to increase.

2.6 Mode 5: above rated constant power

To level off the secondary rotor power in the highest wind speeds, an upper limit is placed on Ω_S , thereby, reducing the variation in mechanical power with azimuth angle. Again, the primary rotor pitch angle is adjusted to maintain a constant primary rotor speed.

3 Control of the secondary rotors

The secondary rotors are enclosed in inner feedback loops with a high bandwidth compared to the controller acting on the primary rotor. Essentially, these sub-systems act as actuators adjusting the tip speed ratio of the secondary rotors in response to the input demand, k_c ; that is,

$$Q_S = k_c \Omega_S^2$$

where Ω_S is the rotor speed and Q_S the aerodynamic torque for a secondary rotor.

Consider that these secondary rotors act independently of each other, see Figure 3, where V_S is the wind speed acting on the rotor, Q_m is the reaction torque from the rotor’s drive-train, Ω_G is the generator speed and ω_e is generator frequency. The input, k_c , is used to regulate the generator frequency, ω_e , and so indirectly the secondary rotor speed, Ω_S . Over a single revolution of the primary rotor, the wind speed acting on the secondary rotor is sinusoidal causing its rotor speed and generated power to in turn be strongly sinusoidal. In higher above rated wind speeds, these sinusoidal variations become excessive and it becomes necessary to limit their amplitude.

Figure 3: Secondary rotor with independent rotor speed

3.1 Common frequency for the two generators

Figure 4: Secondary rotors with common rotor speed

The situation considered above, whereby the power from the two generators driven by the secondary rotors have independent frequencies as discussed in D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3, is superseded here by requiring a common frequency, ω_e , as depicted in Figure 4. Other than the addition of the index, $i = 1,2$ to indicate the variables for the dynamics of the secondary rotors, $i = 1,2$, the notation for Figure 4 remains the same as for Figure 3. The wind speeds acting on the two generators, V_{S1} and V_{S2} , are different as are the generator reaction torques, Q_{m1} and Q_{m2} , acting on the secondary rotors. The total reaction torque from the secondary rotors acting on the primary rotor is $R_P(T_{m1}+T_{m2})$, where T_{m1} and T_{m2} are the thrusts on rotors 1 and 2, respectively.

The secondary rotor 1 dynamics and secondary rotor 2 dynamics in Figure 4 are those depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Secondary rotor dynamics for rotor $i = 1,2$.

The objective for the controller in Figure 2.4 is to cause the secondary rotors to maintain a constant tip speed ratio; that is, tracking $p\sqrt{Q_m/k_c}$ by ω_e must be achieved over a relatively high bandwidth. The input, k_c , determines the tip speed ratio to be tracked.

3.2 Design of the in Figure 4

The structure of the controller in Figure 4 is shown in Figure 5. It is analogous to the standard approach used for C_{Pmax} tracking on conventional turbines. The filter, C_1 , is included to reduce the impact of measurement noise and other parasitics prior to the nonlinear element. The latter would include any transients occurring when the rotor tracking C_{Pmax} is switched. The element, C_2 , is used to place an upper limit on ω_e . As per the discussion on the controller in Figure 3, this upper limit, $\bar{\omega}_e$, is necessary to prevent excessive sinusoidal variations in secondary rotor speed in higher wind speed. In addition, the element, C_2 , is used to limit the rate of change of ω_e to protect the power electronics. The input, k_c , defines the constant C_p to be tracked, when the secondary rotor rotates into the wind.

Figure 6: Controller in Figure 2.4

The dynamics of the rest of the turbine can be neglected when designing and testing the controller in Figure 6 as follows

1. Design the controller assuming that θ_p in $V_{S1} = R_p\Omega_p + V_0\sin(\theta_p)$ and $V_{S2} = R_p\Omega_p - V_0\sin(\theta_p)$ are constant.
2. Test for a time varying θ_p as would be encountered with a rotating primary rotor when switching between generator 1 and 2 would occur.
3. Test for relatively slowly variations in k_c .

3.3 Secondary rotor controller

The operating strategy is defined by a trajectory on the torque-speed plane. To realise that strategy the cusp point, Ω_{Sc} in Figure 1, must be regulated to lie on that trajectory. For example, during mode one, Ω_{Sc} must track a vertical line on the torque speed plane. To meet this requirement to track the trajectory, the secondary rotors are enclosed in an additional feedback loop, see Figure 7, which has Ω_{Sc} as a sometimes time varying reference input. As this reference input is relatively slowly varying, the closed loop bandwidth achieved by the controller, C_S , is low in comparison to that of the inner feedback in Subsection 3.2. An upper bound is placed on Ω_S by the input, Ω_{SB} . When it is exceeded, the output, $\Omega_S - \Omega_{Sc} - f(\Delta P)\Omega_{Sc}$, is set to zero. As the controller, C_S , includes integral action, the value of k_c , remains frozen until the value of the output again falls below Ω_{SB} . This limits the maximum secondary rotor torque and so generated power as the rotors rotate into and out off the ambient wind. When Ω_{SB} is set to $4\bar{k}\bar{\omega}_e$, where $\bar{k} = 0.99$ and $\bar{\omega}_e$ is the upper limit on generator frequency, it prevents wind-up of the integrator in C_S . As in the case of the embedded controller discussed in Subsection 3.2, the dynamics of the rest of the turbine can be neglected, when designing C_S .

Figure 7: Secondary rotor with independent rotor speed

4 Controller design

Control in below rated wind speed is discussed in Subsection 4.1, the transition from below rated wind speed to above rated wind speed in Subsection 4.2 and above rated wind speed in Subsection 4.3.

4.1 Below rated wind speed control

Mode 1: below rated constant Ω_{Sc}

In the lowest below rated wind speeds, the secondary rotors are controlled such that the rotor speed corresponding to the cusp point in Figure 1 is fixed; that is, $\Omega_{Sc} = \Omega_{S0}$ for an appropriate constant Ω_{S0} , here 22.5 rad/s. The controller, C_S , is designed to achieve a bandwidth for the closed loop system in Figure 7 of 1 rad/s. A simple PI controller suffices, albeit with some additional high frequency shaping to reduce the impact of higher frequency components in Ω_S such as the spectral peaks due to rotational sampling of the wind field.

In Mode 1, the primary rotor is not subject to direct control. As the wind speed reduces, the secondary rotor thrust reduces faster than would occur if the cusp point were tracking a constant power coefficient curve. Unlike the secondary rotor cusp point, the primary rotor speed is not constant but automatically tracks a curve on its torque-rotor speed plane whereby the primary rotor aerodynamic torque balances the torque arising from the combined secondary rotor thrust. This curve is a little lower than the constant power coefficient curve.

Mode 2: C_{Pmax} tracking

In intermediate below rated wind speed, the secondary rotors are controlled to maximise energy capture; that is, the cusp point for the secondary rotor tracks the C_{Pmax} curve on the torque-rotor speed plane. To achieve this objective, the outer feedback loop in Figure 7 is not required. Instead the demand, k_c , is a constant. Specifically, it is assigned the value corresponding to the secondary rotors tracking C_{Pmax} .

As per *below rated constant Ω_{Sc}* operation, the primary rotor is not subject to direct control. In Mode 2, as the wind speed varies, the primary rotor automatically tracks its C_{Pmax} curve on the torque-rotor speed plane.

4.2 Mode 3: pre-emptive pitching

Immediately before reaching rated wind speed, the primary blades are pitched to avoid excessive pitch rates during the transition to above rated operation, see Figure 2 and, for more detail about this transition, Figure 8.

On the curve *ab* in Figure 2, the primary rotor is tracking C_{Pmax} ; that is, its tip speed ratio is held constant at λ_{Pmax} . Following the conventional strategy, depicted in red, the torque and rotational speed be held constant on reaching rated wind speed, *b*. While doing so, the tip speed ratio of the primary rotor reduces along *bc* as the ambient wind speed increases.

In below rated wind speeds, each secondary rotor is operated such that the cusp point in Figure 1 tracks its C_{Pmax} curve until *b* in Figure 8 is reached at rated wind speed. Suppose that the secondary rotors continue to operate with their cusp point unchanged in above rated wind speed, then the

average reaction torque from the secondary rotors over a revolution of the primary rotor would be approximately

$$\bar{Q}_S = (1 + \lambda_p^{-2}/2)\bar{T}_{Sc}R_P$$

where \bar{T}_{Sc} is the average thrust at the cusp point in Figure 1 and λ_p is the primary rotor tip speed ratio. Hence, in above rated wind speeds, \bar{Q}_S would increase as the ambient wind speed increases; that is,

$$\bar{Q}_S = \bar{Q}_{Sr}(1 + \lambda_p^{-2}/2)/(1 + \lambda_{pr}^{-2}/2)$$

where \bar{Q}_{Sr} is the reaction torque at rated wind speed and λ_{pr} is the primary rotor tip speed ratio at rated, see Figure 8 (red line).

Figure 8: Secondary rotors' operational strategy

An amendment is required to the above conventional strategy. Pre-emptive pitching is required to reduce the maximum pitch rate when transiting between below and above rated operation. The operational curve in Figure 8 is modified, between 10m/s and 12.5m/s, by the blue curve, *ac*; that is, $\beta = f(\Omega_P)$ and $\lambda_{Si} = g(\Omega_{Sc})$, where the functions, $f(\cdot)$, and $g(\cdot)$, are chosen to minimise the pitch rate. With regard to the primary rotor, the pitch of the blades increased roughly linearly from 0° at 10m/s wind speed to 9.7° at 12.5m/s.

4.3 Above rated wind speed control

Mode 4: above rated constant torque

When wind speed is above rated, a constant \bar{Q}_S should to be maintained, the green curve in Figure 8. To do so, requires \bar{T}_{Sc} to be reduced with increasing wind speed by the factor $(1 + \lambda_{pm}^{-2}/2)/(1 + \lambda_p^{-2}/2)$, see blue curve in Figure 8, where λ_{pm} is tip speed ratio of the primary rotor corresponding to C_{Pmax} tracking. This is achieved by reducing the rotational speed of the secondary rotors.

With the above strategy in above rated wind speed, the power captured by the secondary rotors increases by a factor of approximately $(1 + \lambda_p^{-2})/(1 + \lambda_{pm}^{-2})$. Since λ_p reduces from roughly 5 at rated wind speed to approximately 2.5 at cut-out wind speed, this increase is substantial.

Mode 4: above rated constant power

It would not be cost-effective to exploit the above enhancement to the power capture fully. Instead, an upper limit of an approximate 6% is placed on this enhancement. The input, Ω_{SB} in Figure 7, is exploited to place an upper limit on Ω_S and thereby trim the variation with azimuth angle of the secondary rotor torque. On reaching this limit, the rotational speed of the secondary rotors is made

constant. The input, Ω_{SB} , can thus be used to regulate the extent of this power enhancement. On the limit that, the variation with azimuth angle is completely removed, the enhancement is reduced to zero.

5 Conclusion

An overview of the design performance of the X-rotor with the controller described in this report is summarised by Figures 9 to Figure 13. The operational strategy consists of the 5 modes described in Section 2. Mode 1 covers the wind speed range 3 to 6 m/s; Mode 2 covers the wind speed range 6 to 10.5 m/s; Mode 3 covers the wind speed range 10.5 to 12.5 m/s; Mode 4 covers the wind speed range 12.5 to 15 m/s; Mode 5 covers the wind speed range 15 to 25 m/s. They designated M1, M2, M3, M4 and M5, respectively on the Figures 9 and Figure 10.,

Figure 9: Power curve for the X-rotor with the controller described here

Figure 10: Control strategy showing tip speed ratios and efficiencies

Figure 11: Torque speed curve for the primary rotor

Figure 12: Thrust speed curve for the secondary rotor

Figure 13: Torque speed curve for the secondary rotor

6 References

- [1] D3.1: Definition of operating strategy
- [2] D3.2: Control simulation model of X -rotor concept
- [3] D3.3: Control design models of X-rotor concept